

Effects of Micro Finance Banks on Small Holder Rice Farmer's Livelihood in Kebbi State

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This study assesses effects of micro finance banks on smallholder rice farmers livelihood in Kebbi state. Data for this study were collected through primary and secondary sources, Yamane's formula was used to determine the sample size. A multi stage sampling technique was employed and simple random sampling was also used to pick the respondent for the study. Socio-economic variables explored revealed that majority (83%) of the small holder rice farmers were males with mean age 41 years and most (47%) having secondary education with mean year of farming experience of 5 years. Majority of (69%) of the smallholder rice farmers were fulltime farmers with a mean family size of 4. Regression results of smallholder rice farmer's livelihood capabilities showed that predictors fit the model significantly well. Human capital and natural capital were negative but significant, financial capital was positive and significant. It was concluded that micro finance bank loan has encourage the smallholder rice farmers to increase their rice production. It is recommended that proper enlightenment be given to smallholder's rice farmers in the study area with a view to improving their livelihood capitals.

Keywords: Microfinance Banks, Smallholder Farmers, Rice Farming, Livelihood Impact,

INTRODUCTION

In developing countries like Nigeria improvement in Productivity through investment in productive ventures, especially in the agricultural sector where majority of the population derive their livelihood is necessary for accelerated economic growth. At low level of income farmers, the accumulation of saving may be difficult under such circumstances, access to loans can help smallholder farmers to undertake investment and increase productivity (Gandhimathi, 2014). There is no doubt that agricultural credit is one of the fundamental ingredients for sustainable agricultural productions, as such it's accessibility and demand is one of the prerequisites for attaining the national goal of reducing poverty and economic development.

Financing agriculture is one of the most important factors necessary for the improvement of the quality and quantity of farm harvest leading to increase farmer's income as well as reducing poverty. One major source of achieving a drastic reduction in poverty and alleviating the poor welfare situation of the smallholder farmers is to increase agricultural productivity.

This will at the micro level, translate to an increase in farm income, food security, poverty reduction, and improved smallholder farmers livelihood (FAOSTAT, 2011). The major task facing the world today is that of feeding the ever increasing population of over seven (7) billion people subjected to climate change and natural resource constraint. FAO (2022) asserted that "the global demand for food is expected to increase by 60% between 2002/2007 to 2050". The global food demand is further compounded by the production of biofuels in the industrialized countries; this alone posed a major stress

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to agricultural food systems. To cope with these challenges, smallholder farmers agriculture needs to effectively play a key role in addressing these challenges especially in developing countries, Millennium Development Goals (MDG, 2022). In Nigeria, the three tiers of government had identified the importance of credit to farming communities and have formulated and implemented agricultural credit policies, programmes and created institutions in order to enable rural farmers acquire credit. The Micro Finance Bank (MFB) is one of such policy inventions in agricultural financing in the country (AKpan *et al*, 2013).

The Micro Finance Banks (MFBs) have emerged as an important source of entrepreneurial finance at the grassroots, level (Gui *et al*, 2017). The failure of the pre-existing smallholder farmers finance schemes such as Nigerian Agricultural and cooperative Bank limited (1972), Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (1978), the Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Corporation (1987), the Community Banks (1990) and the people's Bank of Nigeria (1992), necessitated the establishment of the Micro finance banks (Gui *et al*, 2017), Micro finance is defined as financial service that provides micro credit to the extremely low level income people for self-employment to generate income which facilitates them and their families, (CBN, 2019) the micro finance bank was inaugurated in 2007 and is borne with focus to provide increased access of the poor and low income earners to factors of production especially credit. Presently there are Eight hundred and eighty two microfinance bank, licensed, governed and Monitored by the Central Bank of Nigeria and are in operation in Various locations in the Country (CBN, 2019).

Generally the Micro finance banks main goal is to provide financial service to the low level income people who are traditionally not served by the conventional financial institution. Micro Finance bank helps an individual to become independent economically and provide additional income generating activities. Other services provided by the micro finance banks include saving, loans domestic funds transfer and other formal services that are needed by the economically active poor, micro, small and medium enterprises to conduct and expand their businesses.

Access to micro finance can be viewed as a growth of the efficiency of small holder farmers and contributing to elevating of their livelihoods. Like conventional lenders micro finance charge interest on loans and institute specific repayment plans (CBN 2019). In Kebbi State, there are many microfinance banks located in many local government areas of the state disbursing loans to especially smallholder farmers with a view to improve their productivity and livelihood.

Statement of Research Problem

Agricultural credit constitutes the power or Key to unlock

latent abilities. Opportunities, which in turn act s mover of economic development (Ajekigbe, 2016). Capital is a Key constraint in the process of agricultural development in most developing countries. This is because most farmers developing countries are smallholder farmers with low income levels resulting to Low Saving and investment. Rural credit has proven to be a powerful instrument against poverty reduction leading to food security and development in rural areas.

Agricultural credit enhances productivity and promotes standard of Living by breaking vicious cycle of poverty of farmers. (Gandlimathi, 2014) The Federal Government of Nigeria noted credit as one of the pre-requisite for increase agricultural output, created micro finance bank with mission of improving production of the smallholder farmers, which in turn increase both their productivity and livelihood.

Due to the variability of the factors of production as well as attitudinal behavior of smallholder farmers, it is not certain whether the objectives were achieved. Several studies have been carried out on micro finance credit such as Okoroji *et al*, (2022) who studied microfinance services and agricultural production; a case study of small holder rice farmers in Anambra state, Nigeria. Another research by Enimu *et al* (2016), on the effect of micro finance bank loan on the livelihood of small holder farmers in delta state, Nigeria; likewise Thritha (2013) work on the effect of access to micro credit finance in Nairobi Kenya, Richard (2015), investigation the effects of micro credit on welfare of household in Kenya; Hanad (2010) work on micro credit participation and Nutrition outcomes among women in Peru republic.

Onyeagacha *et al* (2012); who work on loan repayment, its determinant and socioeconomic characteristics of micro finance loan beneficiaries southeast Nigeria. Other studies on livelihood and food security that include Ellies (2000) work on rural livelihood diversity in developing countries Alinovi *et al*, (2010), determinants of livelihood diversification in pastoral societies; Eneyew (2012), work on food security dynamics and correlation among rural households while little or none were found to assess effects of micro finance banks on smallholder rice farmer's livelihood especially in the north Western Nigeria. Different studies at different parts of the world reports on failure of agricultural credit schemes for the smallholder farmers. This situation may likely affect the livelihood of the farmers.

Thus, there is need to understand the present situation and its attendant effect on future accessibility to loan to the small holder farmers. In view of this, the study provided answers to the following research questions, with regards to the effects of microfinance bank on smallholder rice fanner's livelihood in Kebbi State:

- i. What are the socio-economic characteristics of smallholder rice farmers in the study area?
- ii. What is the livelihood capability of the smallholder rice

farmers in the study area?

- iii. What are the effects of MFB on the livelihood of the small holder rice farmers in the study area?
- iv. What is the gross margin of the smallholder rice farmers in the study area?
- v. What are the constraints faced by small holder rice farmers in securing loan from MFBs in the study area?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The broad objective of the study was to assess the effects of microfinance bank on smallholder rice farmer's livelihood in Kebbi state.

The specific objectives were to:

- i. Describe the socio-economic characteristics of the smallholder rice farmers in the study area.
- ii. Evaluate the smallholder rice farmers livelihood Capability in the study area.
- iii. Determine the effects of MFB on the livelihood of the small holder rice farmers in the study area.
- iv. Analyze the gross margins of the smallholder rice farmers in the study area.
- v. Determine the constraints faced by the small holder rice farmers in securing loan from MFB in the study area.

Justification of the Study

Generally, there is an acceptance of the important role of farm credit and a wide appreciation by most government of the need for credit in agriculture. Agricultural credit is fundamental to development of household livelihood which can help farmers to maximize their economic potentials.

The findings of the study will provide basis for policy makers in developing an appropriate policy mix, as well as increased agricultural production. It is anticipated that this study will also contribute to available literature on micro finance bank credit. To credit institutions, it is expected to assist them when evaluating credit. Programmes and policy variable to form workable Credit framework in the state and nation in general.

CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Eliminating hunger and poverty is the primary goal to achieve world peace and sustainable development. It is also suggested by the World Bank that a achieving Sustainable livelihoods for rural households plays a significant role in the united Nation's 2030 Agenda (Bank 2011).

As an integral part of sustainable development, poverty alleviation and environmental protection have become the common concern in the global community.

Sustainable livelihoods is one of the Key Issues concerning strategies of the rural poor, in the recent time researches on livelihoods give much emphasis on livelihoods at the micro-level (Qi, un, Cheng, and Ye, 2015).

As a worldwide issue poverty has been measured in various ways, such as income, consumption assets and multi-dimensional view. As part of the continual development of Poverty Measuring approaches, Sustainable livelihood is deemed to be more reasonable which also covers the multi-dimensional aspects in tracking poverty.

Developed by the department for international development (DFID) in the mid-1980s, the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA) is defined to improve its assets under external impacts. (Chen et al, 2013). It has become popular in development thinking as a way of conceptualizing rural development, poverty reduction and environmental Management, which is also an assets based Conceptual framework that has been widely used by researchers and policy Makers. (Chen *et al*, 2013). As asset, portpolio is considered natural, physical, financial, human and social capital (Yahaya and Al. Amin, 2016).

Sustainability of natural resources can meet the needs of present and future generations, and a sustainable livelihood strategy needs to bring a positive Synergy between natural capital and other Capitals to lift the poor out of poverty (Ceinkaiya, *et al*, 2014).

Natural and human capitals exhibit a positive correlation with the farm livelihood strategy, while financial and social capitals are the catalyst for driving non-farm activities only by enhancing capital capacity and access to capitals can the issue of livelihood capitals be solved in the long term Fang *et al*, (2014).

Sustainable livelihood (SLF) has been adopted as theoretical approach to help understand and analyze the livelihood of small holder farmers in the study area. The (SLF) is a particular form of livelihood analysis used by a growing number of researchers and applied development organizations including the Department for international development of the United Kingdom, the UNDP as well as nongovernmental organization.

In view of this issue, finding out the key elements and Key path of smallholder farmers sustainable Livelihoods is the pre-condition of precise poverty alleviation and sustainable development of the smallholder farmers. Sustainable livelihood approach entails how people use their resources to cope and adapt to uncertain and unpredictable natural events, in addition to the support they receive from governments and non-governmental institutions.

The smallholder rice farmers utilized their credit receive from microfinance bank and pursue their livelihood with mission of improving their livelihood outcomes, which will help them to develop themselves and improve their livelihoods. Based on this idea, a conceptual model is develop to guide this study as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Frame work
 Source: adopted from DFID 2002 with modification by the researcher

KEY:
 H = Human Capital
 N = Natural Capital
 F = Financial Capital
 S = social capital
 P = Physical Capital

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Kebbi state, in the north-western Nigeria with its capital at Birnin Kebbi, located

between latitude 10°05¹N and 13°27¹ and longitude 3°35¹E and 6°03¹. It covers a land area of 36, 800 Sq Km². It is boarded by Niger and Benin Republics to the west and by States of Sokoto and Zamfara state in the north east and Niger state to the south. (KSG, 2013). The state has a total projected population of 3,256,541 people

Figure 2. Map of the Study Area.

(2006 census) and 4,738,267 people (2019 Approximate using 3.5% growth rate). Kebbi State is made up of four emirate zones of Gwandu, Argungu, Yauri, and Zuru. Consisting of 21 Local Government Areas and is

populated by diverse ethnic groups, prominent among which are Hausa, Fulani, Zabarmawa, Lelna (Dakarkari), Kambari, Arawa and Dukkawa. The population is largely rural with more than two-thirds of the population

Table 1: Present the sampling frame and sample size of the study

Local Govts.	Villages	Sampling Frame	Sample Size
Argungu	Argungu	850	49
	Gulma	520	30
Birnin Kebbi	Ambursa	600	35
	Makera	450	26
Bagudo	Bagudo	760	44
	Gwamba	390	22
Suru	Suru	800	46
	Aljannare	350	20
Yauri	Yauri	650	38
	Tondi	380	22
Zuru	Zuru	460	27
	Ushe	315	18
Total 6	12	6525	377

Source: Microfinance Bank: year 2023

Table 2 Indicators of Livelihood Capital.

Livelihood Capital	Indicators Variable	Implication	Formula
Human capital (C₁)	Labour capacity (C ₁₁)	Labour ability of each family member was assigned as full labour(1), half labour(0.5) and off labour(0). The labour ability values of all family members was summed and standardized.	$C_1 = C_{11} + C_{12} + C_{13} + C_{14}$
	Education level (C ₁₂)	The education level of each family member was assigned as college and above (1), secondary school (0.75), JSS (0.5), primary school (0.25) and no capital western education (0). The education level values of all family members was be summed and standardized.	
	Age level (C ₁₃)	The age values of each family members was assigned 15-29=2, 30-49=3, 50-59=1, 60-69=0.8. The age values of all family members was summed and standardized.	
	Health level (C ₁₄)	The assigned health values of each family member depicts the frequency of illness of a member as was assigned often-ill (0), Moderate (1), good (2), very good (3). The health values of all family members was summed and standardized.	
Natural capital (C₂)	Cultivated land for (C ₂₁)	Index of rice cultivated land, was the standardized rice cultivated land area in hectare per capital	$C_2 = C_{21} + C_{22} + C_{23}$
	Cultivated land for crops (C ₂₂)	Index of other crops cultivated land, was the standardized cultivated land area in hectare per capital	
	Yield of crop per unit area (C ₂₃)	Index of yield per unit area, was the standardized per crop yield in kg per capital.	
Physical capital (C₃)	Physical equipment (C ₃₁)	Physical equipment includes motor vehicle, motor equipment cycle, machines etc. a value of 1 was added for each type of physical equipment that the family has. The index of physical equipment was the standardized sum of physical equipment value.	$C_3 = C_{31} + C_{32}$
	Livestock (C ₃₂)	The primary livestock type may include camel, horse, cattle, sheep, goat and chicken, weighted as 1, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2 and 0.1 respectively. The livestock capital of one household was the sum of each livestock number multiplied by its weight. The index of livestock capital was the standardized livestock capital of the potential sample respondent.	

Table 2. Contd.

	Housing condition (C ₃₃)	Housing size was weighted as; 5 rooms (1), 4 rooms (0.75), 3rooms (0.5), 2 rooms (0.25), 1 room (0). Housing type was weighted as; cement/concrete house (1), mud brick house (0.75), mud/cement house (0.5), tent (0.25) and thatched cottage (0). The index of each housing condition was the standardized sum of each housing situation multiplied by its weight. A households' financial capital may be primarily from total income from the past year or cash savings in naira. The index of cash income was the standardized cash income per capita.	
Financial capital (C₄)	Access to low interest loan (C ₄₂)	Formal financial institution (banks, credit cooperatives) and individual lenders (family and friends). The index of access to low interest loan was the standardized sum of each loan secured per capita.	$C_4=C_{41}+C_{42}$
Social capital (C₅)	Leadership potentials (C ₅₁)	There was significant social capital for family capital potentials members employed in government agencies or (C5) (C51) company, with access to a stable income and other assistances. If a family member engages in any government/company/NGO then its value was weighted (1) and otherwise is (0). Rate of opposition during a community meeting is weighted; often (1), usual (0.75), sometimes (0.5), few (0.25), never (0). The index of leadership potential was the standardized sum of a leadership situation multiplied by its weighted value.	$C_5=C_{51}+C_{22}+C_{53}$
	Confidence (C ₅₂)	Grades of confidence in people around the community weighted as; all (1), most (0.75); half (0.5), little (0.25) or none (0). The index of confidence was the standardized sum of a confidence multiplied by its weighted value.	
	Relatives (C ₅₃)	The index of relatives was standardized number of relatives in the township.	
		Total Livelihood Capital (C) =C ₁ +C ₂ +C ₃ ±C ₄ +C ₅	

Source: Adopted from Wang *et al.* 2015; Fang *et al.*, 2021

depending on agriculture for their livelihoods (KARDA 2007). The state has two distinct climatic seasons. The dry season generally characterized by high temperatures lasting seven to eight months ranging from November to May, the weather between March and June is hot with temperatures usually between 38°C to 42°C. The rainy season last for four to five months in a year, which usually begins in early May, while the heavy fall is experienced between July and August. The climate of the study area encourages the production of crops and animals both during rainy and dry seasons of the year, which makes majority of the inhabitants to choose farming as an occupation. (KSG, 2018).

The state is richly endowed with fadama flood plains of river Niger and Rima and their tributaries that transverse the state with alluvial soil suitable for rain fed and irrigated Farming. Some people also engaged in fishing activities.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

A Multi-stage Sampling technique was employed in the Selection of sample size in the study. First stage involved Purposive selection of six Local Government Areas (Argungu, Birnin Kebbi, Yauri, Zuru, Suru and Bagudo) known to have smallholder rice producing farmers with at least one situated microfinance Bank in the area. Stage two obtaining a Sample frame from the micro finance banks situated in the purposive Selected Banks in order to draw a sample size for the Study. Stage three involved selection of two communities that have high concentration of rice producing farmers and with loan facility from the each of the six Local Government Areas purposively selected, totalling twelve villages. Stage four, determining the sample size, for the purpose of questionnaire administration, Yamane's formula was used to obtain the sample size and a simple random

Table 3 Evaluation Index of Sustainable Livelihood Capability of Smallholder Rice farmers

Livelihood indicator	Indicator meaning	Indirect reflection	Assignment description
Standard of Living	Safety of food, and drinking water	Food richness, attention to drinking water safety	Significant decreased
Welfare level/social amenities	Welfare like education, health care, roads accessibility/availability	Free/subsidized medical care, child welfare, pregnant women welfare etc	(1) Decrease (2)
Level of income	Income level	Per capita income	No change (3) Increase (4)
Employment level	Employment opportunities	Diversity in Employment	Significant increase (5)
Rural attachment	Pride in and attachment to community and home	Pride and sense of belonging	

sampling was also used to pick the respondents for the study. The formula is stated thus.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$n = \frac{6525}{1 + 6525(0.052)} = \frac{6525}{17.3} = 377$$

n = sample size
 N = population
 e = Margin error (5%)

selection of each village sample size was done using the formula stated as

$$Sz = \frac{n}{N} \times 377$$

Sz sample size per village
 n = number of beneficiaries in each village
 N = population

DATA COLLECTION

Primary data was obtained with the aid of structured questionnaire administered through interview with the help of trained enumerators. Also secondary data was used from Journals, textbooks, Internet and National Bureau of statistics and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical bulletin.

Data Analysis

The analytical tool used for this study was Sustainable livelihood approach.

MODEL SPECIFICATION

Measurement of Livelihood Capital

This research is initiated by identifying the level of sustainable livelihood for the smallholder rice farmers in the study area. Identification of the primary indicators

concerning livelihood capital was based on the relevant literature as it affects the smallholder communities in the study area peculiar to it. The research selected a number of indicators to represent the attributes of livelihood capital (i.e. human capital, natural capital, financial capital, physical capital and social capital) in the study area. Table 2 lists the relevant details of the indicators.

Please note: standardization means to calculate the mean and standard deviation for a variable then for each observed value of the variable you subtract the mean and divide the standard deviation.

Sustainable Livelihood Capability

This study set up indicators for sustainable livelihood capability to include; the standard of living, welfare level, income level, employment opportunities, rural attachment etc. Table 3 quantitatively measures smallholder rice farmers’ sustainable livelihood capability. The likart scale was used to measure livelihood perception of the smallholder rice farmers.

Model of livelihood capitals among smallholder rice farmers

The model was based on the objective to evaluate the respondents’ sustainable livelihood capabilities in the study area. The set of livelihood capital may exhibit a direct influence on smallholder rice farmers’ sustainable livelihood capability. The values obtained were aggregated and used in a regression equation that was established for the purpose as established by (Fang *et al.*, 2021)

$$SL_1 = \delta_0 + \delta_1 H_1 + \delta_2 N_2 + \delta_3 F_3 + \delta_4 S_4 + \delta_5 P_5 + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where

SL_i = Sustainable livelihood capability as perceived by smallholder rice farmers (1474)
 δ₀ = constant term to be determined

Table 4. Regression Results of Small Holder Rice Farmers Livelihood Capabilities.

Variable	Coefficient (b)	Std error	T	P. values
Constant	2.576	0.065	39.562	0.000
HC	0.349	0.014	-25.167	0.000
NC	-0.350	0.014	-25.779	0.000
PC	-0.001	0.005	-0.232	0.817
FC	0.350	0.014	25.871	0.000
SC	0.010	0.007	1.452	0.147
R ²	0.665			
Adjusted R ²	0.660			

Source: Field survey 2023

$\delta_1 - \delta_5$ = regression coefficients to be determined

H= human capital (155.16)
 N= natural capital (1731.93)
 F= Financial capital (3380.35)
 S= Social capital (1937.02)
 P= physical capital (1988.24)
 μ = as residual term

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The regression results of the small holder rice farmers livelihood capabilities who have acquired MFB loan in the study area is presented in Table 4.

From Table 4. it can be seen that the predictors fits the model significantly well. The model shows a perfect and significant correlation between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable ($R = 0.815$, $p < 0.05$). All the variation of the dependent variable were accounted for by the predictors ($R^2 = 0.665$). This shows that the predictors have significant influence on the response ($P < 0.05$), thus confirming the hypothesis that overall livelihood capital positively influence sustainable livelihood of the small holder rice farmers, but the extent to which each type of capital affects livelihood capability is different.

When all the values of the predictors were kept constant the response is 2.576 and is significant ($P < 0.05$). An increase of one unit of human capital (HC) and natural capital (NC) each, lowers the livelihood by one unit respectively and are significant ($P < 0.05$).

Microfinance bank loan can be used to increase the human and natural capital of the smallholder farmers, though the objective of the credit to smallholder farmers is to increase their production level, this will cause an increase in their income and ultimately their livelihood (Mulatu, 2020).

Ahmed (2001) reported that human capital is skills, knowledge, and education, ability of labour and good health that together enables people to pursue their livelihood strategies Human capital is required in order to make use of any of the other types of assets to bring about the improvement of capability. The implication of

this finding could be that the farmers could not attain higher education which will enable them to work in higher positions that will attract much income that will be used to improve their livelihood. Natural capital of farmers represents the natural resources such as land, water, timber and wider environmental goods that are critical for farmers to support production Rapid population growth has to some extent led to accelerate natural capital depletion, people activities tends to temper with natural resources there by reducing their contribution to the development of livelihood.

Physical Capital (PC) is negative and is not significant ($P > 0.05$). Social Capital (SC) is positive but is not significant ($P > 0.005$). The findings of this study is similar to that of Su, *et al.* (2021), who report similar finding in their study on assessment of poverty alleviation measures and sustainable livelihood capability of farm households in rural China. Physical capital includes personal housing and transportation, tools etc and can affect farmers sustainable livelihood capability. (Peng and Zhou, 2021). There is usually lack of physical capital in rural areas and access to microfinance bank credit is an essential factor in reducing lack of physical capital. Social capital is implicit but it can improve social efficiency and integration through cooperation with other people as is it the case with microfinance bank loan processing. This kind of connection between individual, organizations and others can promote the improvement of individual ability, income, and social status. It can thus improve the sustainable livelihood capability of the farmers (Kofarmata and Danlami, 2019).

Financial capital, such as savings, cash flows and credits providing organization, includes the different financial resources used by people to attain their livelihood objectives (Gebru *et al.*, 2018), the primary sources of financial capital include access to formal credit facilities and family income with a combination of savings, off-farm income, on farm income and remittance The on farm income was the primary source of income for smallholder farmers livelihood in developing countries (Isar, *et al.* (2017), excepting the earned income, the most general types of cash flows were pensions, or other transfer from the state (Gebru *et al.*, 2018). Increased

access to microfinance credit provides households with an enhanced ability to diversify their income stream and improves their livelihood (Abeje *et al.*, 2019). The finding of this study showed that, a unit increase in financial capital (FC) improves livelihood by 1.00 and a significant, which implies that the more income generating activities engaged by farmers the more improved livelihood in the study area.

CONCLUSION

In the context of the result obtained, it is concluded that all kind of livelihood capitals will influence the livelihood capability of the farmers, however due to the differences in livelihood capital owned by farmers, the degree of the influence on sustainable livelihood capability is also different. Many of them have gained experience in farming access to micro finance bank loan has encourage them to enhanced their rice production. Microfinance is viable mechanism for promoting economic empowerment among small holder rice farmers in the study area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

Most of the smallholder rice farmers attained only secondary education, there is the need to encourage them to further their education as this will go a long way in improving their human capital with view to improve their livelihood.

Government and policy makers can leverage the demonstrated success of MFB loans to expand credit programmes tailored for small holder farmers ensuring affordable and accessible loans, along with financial literacy programmes to amplify the positive effects seen in this study.

This study captures the short term effects of MFB loans. Future research could examine how this change sustains over multiple farming seasons.

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